

Comparative Study of Sociodemographic Profiles and Fetal Outcomes in Teenage and Adult Mothers

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Abstract:

Background: Teenage pregnancy poses significant health risks to both mothers and their infants due to various socio-demographic challenges. These include lower educational attainment, higher unemployment rates, and poorer socioeconomic conditions compared to adult mothers.

Aim: This study aims to compare the socio-demographic profiles and fetal outcomes of teenage mothers with those of adult mothers.

Methods: A comparative observational study was conducted at the Obstetrics & Gynecology Department of G. M. C. H. Purnea from October 2023 to March 2024. A total of 200 mothers (100 teenage, 100 adult) were enrolled. Data on socio-demographic variables and fetal outcomes were collected through structured interviews and medical record reviews. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0.

Results: Teenage mothers had significantly lower education levels (60% vs. 25%), higher unemployment rates (70% vs. 40%), and lower socioeconomic status (75% vs. 45%) compared to adult mothers ($p < 0.001$ for all). Fetal outcomes indicated higher rates of preterm births (20% vs. 10%, $p = 0.045$), low birth weight (25% vs. 15%, $p = 0.050$), and NICU admissions (18% vs. 8%, $p = 0.039$) among teenage mothers. No significant differences were observed in stillbirths and congenital anomalies between the groups.

Conclusion: Teenage mothers face substantial socio-demographic disadvantages and adverse fetal outcomes compared to adult mothers. These findings underscore the need for targeted interventions to improve educational opportunities, employment prospects, and prenatal care for teenage mothers.

Recommendations: Policies and programs should focus on enhancing socio-economic conditions, providing comprehensive prenatal care, and offering mental health support to teenage mothers to improve their maternal and fetal health outcomes.

Keywords: Socio Demographic Profile, Fetal Outcomes, Preterm Birth, Low Birth Weight.

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Introduction

Adolescent pregnancy is still a major global public health concern that has a substantial impact on the health of both the mother and the foetus. (WHO) has drawn attention to the increased risks that come with teenage pregnancies, including increased incidence of problems like low birth weight, preterm birth, and admissions to the neonatal intensive care unit (NICU). Compared to adult mothers, teenage moms frequently confront a distinct set of socio-demographic obstacles that can increase these risks, including as lower educational attainment, higher unemployment rates, and inferior socioeconomic position [1].

According to recent research, there are significant distinctions between teenage and adult moms in terms of these socio-demographic characteristics

and how they affect the course of pregnancies. For example, in a study discovered that hazardous behaviours, under nutrition, and poor prenatal care were among the characteristics that made adolescent moms more likely to have unfavourable foetal outcomes. These results are in line with a cross-sectional study that found that compared to their adult counter parts, teenage moms had considerably greater rates of preterm births, low birth weight babies, and NICU admissions [2].

There is ample evidence linking socio-demographic characteristics to unfavourable pregnancy outcomes in adolescent moms. Teenage moms, for instance, frequently come from lower socioeconomic origins, which may restrict their access to quality education and healthcare. A study demonstrated that low

socioeconomic level was a major predictor of unfavourable foetal outcomes among adolescent mothers, demonstrating how this lack of resources might contribute to inferior pregnancy outcomes [3].

Poorer health outcomes can also be attributed to the psychological and social stresses that teenage moms experience. A 2021 study found that adolescent moms are more likely to suffer from anxiety and depression during pregnancy, which can have a detrimental effect on the health of the mother and the foetus. The study emphasised how crucial it is to offer teenage moms complete support services in order to treat these mental health issues and enhance the success of their pregnancies.

Socio demographic characteristics that limit access to high-quality prenatal care and raise the chance of unfavourable outcomes make teenage pregnancy a serious concern for both moms and their unborn children. Targeted initiatives that improve the financial circumstances of adolescent mothers, expand their access to healthcare and education, and offer strong mental health support are necessary to address these inequities. It is feasible to lessen the differences between adolescent and adult pregnancies by improving the health and wellbeing of young moms and their offspring by addressing these underlying problems.

This study aims to provide insights into the differences in socio demographic profiles and fetal outcomes between teenage and adult mothers, potentially guiding interventions and policies to improve maternal and fetal health

Methodology

Study Design: This study is a comparative, observational study aimed at analyzing the socio demographic profiles and fetal outcomes in teenage versus adult mothers.

Study Setting: The study will be conducted in the Obstetrics & Gynecology Department of G.M.C.H. Purnea.

Participants: A total of 200 participants will be enrolled in the study, comprising 100 teenage mothers (aged 13-19) and 100 adult mothers (aged 20-35).

Study Duration: The study will be conducted over a period of six months, from October 2023 to March 2024.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Teenage mothers aged 13-19 years.
2. Adult mothers aged 20-35 years.
3. Singleton pregnancies.
4. Mothers who consent to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Mothers with pre-existing chronic medical conditions (e.g., diabetes, hypertension).
2. Multiple pregnancies (e.g., twins, triplets).
3. Mothers with a history of substance abuse.
4. Incomplete medical records.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, participants will be randomly selected from the patient population meeting the inclusion criteria. Information bias will be reduced by using standardized data collection forms and procedures.

Data Collection: Data will be collected through structured interviews and review of medical records. Information on sociodemographic variables, maternal health, prenatal care, and fetal outcomes will be gathered.

Procedure

1. Recruitment of participants from the Obstetrics & Gynecology Department.
2. Obtaining informed consent from all participants.
3. Conducting structured interviews and reviewing medical records.
4. Collecting data on socio demographic variables, maternal health status, prenatal care, and fetal outcomes.
5. Ensuring data accuracy and completeness through double-checking and verification.

Statistical Analysis: Data will be analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics will be used to summarize the socio demographic profiles and fetal outcomes. Comparative analyses (e.g., chi-square tests, t-tests) will be conducted to identify significant differences between teenage and adult mothers. A p-value of <0.05 will be considered statistically significant.

Results

Participants: A total of 200 mothers participated in the study, with 100 teenage mothers (aged 13-19) and 100 adult mothers (aged 20-35). The socio demographic characteristics and fetal outcomes of both groups were analyzed.

Table 1: Socio demographic Characteristics of Teenage and Adult Mothers

Characteristic	Teenage Mothers (n=100)	Adult Mothers (n=100)	p-value
Mean Age (years)	17.2 ± 1.5	27.3 ± 3.2	<0.001
Education Level (% below high school)	60%	25%	<0.001
Employment Status (% unemployed)	70%	40%	<0.001
Marital Status (% married)	80%	95%	0.002
Socioeconomic Status (% low income)	75%	45%	<0.001

Table 2: Fetal Outcomes in Teenage and Adult Mothers

Outcome	Teenage Mothers (n=100)	Adult Mothers (n=100)	p-value
Preterm Birth (% <37 weeks)	20%	10%	0.045
Low Birth Weight (% <2500g)	25%	15%	0.050
Neonatal ICU Admission (%)	18%	8%	0.039
Stillbirth (%)	5%	2%	0.284
Congenital Anomalies (%)	4%	3%	0.707
Apgar Score <7 at 5 min (%)	22%	12%	0.046

Discussion

The study, which took place over six months at the Obstetrics & Gynaecology Department of G. M. C. H. Purnea, involved 200 participants: 100 adult moms aged 20-35 and 100 teenage mothers aged 13-19. The results showed significant differences in the two groups' socio demographic profiles and foetal outcomes. Compared to adult mothers, teenage moms had a lower mean age (17.2 vs. 27.3 years), higher unemployment rates, worse socioeconomic position, and lower levels of education. More specifically, 75% of adolescent mothers came from low-income homes, 70% were unemployed, and 60% of adolescent mothers had just completed high school. Furthermore, 80% of adolescent moms were not married, compared to 95%.

Foetal outcomes revealed that preterm births (20% vs. 10%), low birth weight infants (25% vs. 15%), and neonatal ICU admissions (18% vs. 8%) were more common among young moms. Additionally, babies born to adolescent moms had a greater prevalence of poor Apgar scores (<7 at 5 minutes) (22% vs. 12%). Nonetheless, there was no discernible difference in the rates of congenital defects and stillbirths across the groups. These results emphasise the need for focused efforts to improve prenatal care and address the socioeconomic difficulties young moms encounter in order to reduce the risks associated with adolescent pregnancies and improve the health of both the mother and the foetus.

Preterm delivery, low birth weight, and perinatal morbidity are among the pregnancy-related issues that adolescent moms are far more likely to experience. For example, compared to adult mothers, adolescent moms experienced increased rates of undernutrition, preterm births, postpartum haemorrhage, and premature rupture of membranes (PROM) [4].

According to a study conducted in which teenage pregnancies are linked to greater rates of neonatal problems, such as low birth weight and higher neonatal mortality. According to the study, compared to adult mothers, adolescent moms had a

greater rate of preterm birth and lower Apgar scores at birth [5].

According to research conducted in which teenage moms had higher rates of anaemia, low birth weight, intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR), and hypertension than did adult mothers. This suggests that teenage pregnancies carry a higher risk of complications for both the mother and the foetus [6].

Conclusion

This research highlights the differences between adolescent and adult mothers' socio demographic profiles and foetal outcomes. To improve the health and wellbeing of moms and their kids, it is imperative to address these inequities through social support networks and comprehensive healthcare.

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